

Development of Balinese Script Learning Media Animation Based on Wana Kerthi Approach

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Abstract

This study aims to develop an interactive learning media for Balinese script using the *Wana Kerthi* approach through 2D animation. The integration of animation and music is intended to enhance children's understanding and interest in learning the Balinese script while simultaneously introducing them to environmental conservation concepts. The research method includes observation, interviews, and questionnaires distributed to educators and parents. The media development process consists of three stages: pre-production (research, concept design, and storyboard creation), production (animation and music development), and post-production (final editing and integration). The test results indicate that the developed learning media is feasible and effective, with an approval rating of 83.3% from media experts, 88% from content experts, and 90.1% from users. These results demonstrate that the combination of 2D animation and music enhances engagement and retention in learning Balinese script. Future research is recommended to expand the variety of musical elements, increase language content, and improve animation quality to further optimize its effectiveness in early childhood education.

Keywords: *Balinese script, Wana Kerthi, 2D animation, interactive learning, early childhood education.*

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Introduction

Widespread digital development has made it easier for children to access information through digital devices. Electronic games and social media platforms such as TikTok, Instagram and YouTube have become part of their daily lives (Kurniawan et al., 2024). While providing benefits in terms of entertainment and education, exposure to age-inappropriate digital content can cause a shift in cultural values and weaken children's character. As a result, children tend to forget their local wisdom and cultural heritage (N. A. S. Putra et al., 2023; Setiawan et al., 2023). Therefore, efforts to instill cultural values must begin at an early age to build awareness and a strong cultural identity in children (Fleer, 2020; Saracho, 2023).

The introduction of culture should start from fundamental aspects such as regional language. Balinese, as the mother tongue of the Balinese people, plays an important role in daily communication as well as in the preservation of local culture (Susiani, 2021). This language is not only a means of communication, but also the main medium in transmitting cultural values through various forms of literature, songs, and oral traditions (Sari & Asmendri, 2020).. Balinese script, as part of the Balinese writing system, has unique shapes and characteristics that are different from Latin letters. However, uninteresting learning methods often cause children difficulties in understanding and memorizing Balinese Script (Sudarma et al., 2024).

In Balinese culture, there is the concept of *Wana Kerthi*, which is a teaching about preserving forests as part of the Sad Kerthi philosophy (Muku et al., 2025; I. N. A. S. Putra & Mudra, 2022). Forests have an

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essential role in the ecosystem as well as in the lives of Balinese Hindus. The concept of *Wana Kerthi* has long been applied in Balinese traditions, such as the celebration of Tumpek Wariga/Tumpek Uduh, the existence of Alas Angker Temple, and customary rules (*awig-awig*) that regulate forest protection (Dewi, 2017). Therefore, it is important to introduce this concept to children from an early age as part of local wisdom-based education (Ernawati et al., 2018; Syamsi & Tahar, 2021).

The learning-by-play approach is an effective method in introducing culture to early childhood. Interactive media-based learning can increase their interest and understanding of the material being taught. Based on observations at Dharma Sentana Kindergarten, the method of teaching local culture still uses simple media such as pictures, statues, and frames (Tafonao, 2018). An interview with the Principal of Dharma Sentana Kindergarten revealed that teaching Balinese is mostly done through stories and folk songs, while the introduction of Balinese Script is still limited due to the lack of age-appropriate learning media for children.

One effective method in attracting children's attention is through a combination of music and animation. Cartoon or animation is a form of media that is highly favored by children because of its attractive visuals and funny characters (Ibrahim et al., 2023). Therefore, the introduction of Balinese Script can be packaged in the form of songs combined with 2D animations with animal characters and forest backgrounds as a representation of the *Wana Kerthi* concept. In this way, children not only learn to recognize Balinese Script but also gain an understanding of the importance of environmental conservation (Sudrajat, 2021).

Based on these problems, this research aims to develop learning media for Balinese script based on 2D animation with the *Wana Kerthi* approach. This media is expected to be an interesting and effective educational tool for early childhood in recognizing Balinese Script while understanding the values of environmental conservation in Balinese culture.

Materials and Methods

Data Collection Method

This study uses a data collection method that involves observation, interviews, and the distribution of questionnaires to obtain comprehensive information regarding the effectiveness of 2D animation-based Balinese script learning media. Observations were carried out at Dharma Sentana Kindergarten to understand the teaching methods that have been applied in introducing Balinese script to children. Through this observation, an overview of the learning environment, the availability of teaching media, and the children's response to the method used was obtained.

Interviews were conducted with educators to explore their perspectives regarding the obstacles in teaching Balinese script and their hopes for animation-based learning media. This interview focused on the need for more interactive learning media, the challenges in attracting children's attention, and the effectiveness of the methods that have been applied.

In addition, questionnaires were distributed to parents and educators to evaluate the extent to which the learning media developed can help children recognize and understand Balinese script. This questionnaire measures readability, visual appeal, understanding of the material, and the effectiveness of the combination of animation and songs in increasing children's interest in learning.

Design Process Diagram

The design process scheme in this design includes creating a background that contains the background of the problem, then continuing with data collection to support the research (Luna, 2018). From the results of data collection, an analysis was carried out on the data that had been obtained, after which a solution was taken to solve the problems found in the background, namely the Design of 2D Animation-Based *Wana Kerthi* Balinese Script Learning Media. From this solution, a realization process consisting of three stages was carried out. The first is the pre-production stage, which determines the concept, theme,

characters, script, and storyboard that match the solution provided. Then, the production stage begins, which is the stage of making the animation. Audio and the merging of assets are carried out. The post-production stage is the final stage of creating learning media. At this stage, the animated video will be given effects and audio added until the rendering process of the animated video in MP4 format and 1080p resolution.

Figure 1. Design Process Scheme
Source: Priyono et al., 2023

The design process for this learning medium consists of several main stages, namely needs analysis, visual and animation design, media production, and testing and evaluation. This design scheme aims to ensure that the learning media developed is not only attractive to children, but also effective in supporting the Balinese script learning process.

The first stage is a needs analysis, which identifies the needs of users, both from the perspective of children as the target users and educators as learning facilitators. From the results of observations and interviews, it was found that the method of teaching Balinese script is still very limited, so interactive media that is more interesting and easier for children to understand is needed.

Furthermore, visual design and animation were carried out. In this stage, a visual concept was developed that was suitable for early childhood characters. Character illustrations and background elements were designed using Adobe Illustrator to ensure an attractive and educational visual. In addition, 2D animation was developed using Adobe After Effects by applying animation principles such as squash and stretch, anticipation, and timing, so that the character's movements look more natural and interactive.

In the media production stage, all the previously designed elements are combined into a single, complete learning media unit. The educational song containing lyrics in Balinese script is made using FL Studio, with an interesting musical composition to make it easier for children to memorize and recognize Balinese script. The song is then synchronized with the animation that has been created to create a fun and effective learning experience.

The final stage is testing and evaluation. The learning media was tested by involving 30 early childhood children and educators at Dharma Sentana Kindergarten. The evaluation was carried out using a Likert scale-based questionnaire method to assess the effectiveness of the learning media from various aspects, including text readability, visual appeal, children's understanding of the material, and user comfort in accessing the media. The results of this test were analyzed quantitatively to determine the level of success of the learning media developed.

By applying this method, this study aims to ensure that 2D animation-based learning media with the *Wana Kerthi* approach can be an effective solution in improving children's understanding of Balinese script through a more interactive and interesting approach.

Results

Animation Visualization

The Balinese script learning video can be visualized in the following scenes.

In this scene, the monkey and elephant characters are singing a Balinese script song with the addition of a starling extra character at the beginning of the video. The animation technique used in this scene is tweened animation and rigging. This scene is added with karaoke text that uses franklin gothic heavy font to make it easier for children to sing.

Figure 2. Animation Scene (a)
Source: Author's Document, 2025

In this scene, the monkey and elephant characters learn about Balinese script and pengangge script by adding narration by dubbing. The animation technique used is tweened animation and rigging. This scene is added with the shape of each script and explanatory text using franklin gothic heavy font.

Figure 3. Animation Scene (b)
Source: Author's Document, 2025

This scene features a Balinese starling character as a guide in learning Balinese about things in the forest. This scene is added with the Balinese script of each letter and the Latin text of the word using franklin gothic heavy font. The animation technique used in this scene is rigging technique.

Figure 4. Animation Scene (c)
Source: Author's Document, 2025

This scene features a monkey and an elephant playing, with a voice-over narration explaining how to preserve the forest. The animation techniques used in this scene are tweened animation and rigging.

Figure 5. Animation Scene (d)
Source: Author's Document, 2025

Testing Results

Based on the presentation of the test results by media experts, it can be concluded that the learning media for Balinese characters through the *Wana Kerthi* approach is declared feasible with an average percentage of 83.3%. Exposure to the results of testing by material experts can be concluded that the Balinese script learning media through the *Wana Kerthi* approach is declared in accordance with Balinese language learning with a percentage of 88%. The presentation of the test results by users can be concluded that the learning media for Balinese characters through the *Wana Kerthi* approach is declared feasible as learning Balinese characters for children with a percentage of 90.1%.

Discussion

A) Pre-Production Stage

The pre-production stage is the initial stage of creating a work, starting from data collection to storyboard creation, which will serve as a guide in the next stage.

Research

In this stage, the writer collects data such as conducting observations, interviews, documentation, questionnaires, and literature studies to determine the theme and concept to support the creation of this learning medium. From the results of the research, it can be concluded that this Balinese script learning medium will be presented in the form of 2D animation with the concept of a music video. The song or music used is specially made with Balinese script as the lyrics. During the song breaks, simple words in Balinese language and script related to *Wana Kerthi* will be inserted according to the theme used, which is the forest.

Wana Kerthi Approach

Wana Kerthi is a concept of preserving and maintaining the sanctity of the forests in Bali. So that the concept of *Wana Kerthi* will be presented in the Balinese script learning media as a theme and additional material in 2D animation videos. The theme taken is the forest according to the concept of *Wana Kerthi* and additional material that will be inserted in the Balinese script song breaks such as the introduction of words related to the forest in the form of Balinese and Balinese script as well as how to protect the forest and the environment.

Depiction of Assets

The depiction of assets in this learning medium is adapted to the theme and concept that has been designed. From these themes and concepts, the character assets used in this 2D animation-based learning medium are animals found in the forest, namely monkeys and elephants. These animal character assets are made as cute as possible to attract children's attention. Other assets such as forest backgrounds, trees, to Balinese script vectors are adapted to the theme raised, namely the *Wana Kerthi* approach.

Figure 6. Animation Scene (d)
Source: Author's Document, 2025

Synopsis

The intro will show the bright shining sun and then go to the scenery section where it will show mountains, forests and pristine streams. Next, the animal characters are busy playing in the forest and then a voice over invites the animals to sing a Balinese alphabet song. The animals sing happily, then during the break of the Balinese alphabet song, the voice over begins to tell about how Balinese people preserve trees and forests and invite the animals to help plant trees to protect the forest. In addition, a few words in Balinese related to the forest will be inserted, such as Woh, Buron, Alas, Tukad, Punyan,

which are changed using Balinese script. Then it continues with singing the Balinese alphabet song and ends with the animal characters waving their hands.

B) Production Process

The production of Balinese alphabet learning media with a *Wana Kerthi* approach based on 2D animation can be explained as follows.

Illustration of Asset Images

The process of making characters and assets in this 2D animation video was created using Adobe Illustrator CC 2019 Software. In the creation of asset illustrations, visual communication design elements are used, namely lines, shapes, and colors, resulting in a harmonious design composition. The stages in the creation of characters and assets are as follows:

Worksheet Size

In the creation of characters and assets, the file layout size used is 1920 x 1080 px which corresponds to the animation resolution to be made, namely HD 1080p.

Outline Creation

The outline creation process is adjusted to the manual sketch that has been made previously. Furthermore, the outline creation is continued digitally using Adobe Illustrator CC 2019. Some of the tools used are pen tools, rectangle tool, shape boilder tool, selection tool, and direct selection tool.

Coloring Outline

The outline of the characters and previously created assets will be colored using several tools such as the fill tool, eyedropper, and color picker. The color used is a tertiary color, resulting in a color that tends to be soft and not too contrasting so as not to disturb children's vision.

Figure 7. Character Coloring
Source: Author's Document, 2025

Concept

The concept applied to this learning medium is a collaboration between a music video and 2D animation where the music and song used are made specifically for this animated video. This song contains an introduction to Balinese script, namely *Ha, Na, Ca, Ra, Ka, Da, Ta, Sa, Wa, La, Ma, Ga, Ba, Nga, Pa, Ja, Ya, Nya* in Latin letters. Then it uses the *Wana Kerthi* approach as a theme and additional material that is included in the break of the Balinese script song. The material inserted related to *Wana Kerthi* such as how to preserve the forest and the addition of simple Balinese words that are still related to *Wana Kerthi* are then transformed into Balinese script such as *Woh, Buron, Alas, Don, Tukad, Yeh, Punyan, Danyuh, Batu, Sunar* which are explained through dubbing/voice over to produce an animated video that can be accepted by young children.

Animation Techniques

The animation technique used in learning media, namely Tweened animation technique, is the process of animating movement by determining the initial keyframe and final keyframe, then running the animation in between the initial and final frame positions. The Rigging technique is the process of animating movement using a puppet tool that is placed on the character's asset so that the character can be moved according to the body joints. For example, the movement of the head where the puppet tool is placed on the neck and head so that it can be moved.

Basic Principles of Animation

The basic principles of animation used are as follows:

Arcs

This principle is used to give a natural and dynamic impression because the movement of the character forms a pattern. This principle is used in the scene of a bird jumping from a tree branch.

Figure 8. Arcs

Source: Author's Document, 2025

Secondary Action

This principle is used to make the movement of the character appear more lively because basically there is no single movement. This principle is applied to several scenes, one of which is when the monkey is hanging before singing.

Figure 9. Secondary Action

Source: Source: Author's Document, 2025

Exaggeration

This principle is used to provide a dramatic effect that is exaggerated so that the animation becomes more interesting. This principle is used in the scene of the sun rotating.

Squash and Stretch

This principle is used to add a bending effect to an object so that the resulting movement looks more lifelike. This principle is used on some objects such as grass.

Sound

This Balinese literacy learning media video uses several types of sound, such as background sound, songs, sound effects, and narration. The following are the types of sound used:

Background sound

The background sound used in this animated video is gamelan music made by myself using the FL Studio 20 application. The instruments used are the Jublag, Jegogan, Kajar, and Ugal gamelan. The gamelan rhythm is made smooth and loud to produce gamelan accompaniment that matches the concept of the animated video.

Song

In this animated video, the song is used as teaching material for learning Balinese script. The song was made by myself using Balinese script as the lyrics, such as *Ha, Na, Ca, Ra, Ka, Da, Ta, Sa, Wa, La, Ma, Ga, Ba, Nga, Pa, Ja, Ya, Nya*.

Sound Effect

The sound effects used in this animated video are the sounds of birds, babies, and water.

Narration

The voiceover in this animation is a female voice with a clear sound character. The narration explains things in the forest in Balinese and how to preserve the forest.

Conclusion

This study has succeeded in designing and developing a 2D animation-based learning medium with the *Wana Kerthi* approach to introduce Balinese script to children. This medium not only functions as a tool for learning script, but also as a means of education regarding environmental preservation through the *Wana Kerthi* concept. The results of the test show that this medium is effective in increasing children's understanding of Balinese script with a high level of success. Based on the results of testing by media experts, this learning medium received a feasibility score of 83.3%, while testing by subject matter experts showed that this medium is suitable for learning Balinese with an approval rate of 88%. In addition, user testing shows that this medium is suitable for use as a learning tool with an effectiveness rate of 90.1%. From these results, it can be concluded that this 2D animation-based learning medium has a positive impact on improving children's understanding of Balinese script and instilling environmental conservation values from an early age. The effectiveness of this medium shows that visual and audio-based learning methods have great potential to strengthen memory and increase children's interest in learning. For further development, it is recommended that the songs and music used be more varied with diverse instruments to avoid boredom in children. In addition, the use of Balinese in this learning medium can be expanded by adding more examples of words and sentences relevant to everyday life.

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